

**CORRECTION OF THE MAJOR ERROR
IN ELECTROMAGNETIC THEORY
AND
TRANSITION TO THE ALICE LAW**

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I – PREFACE

In today's Electromagnetic Theory, the speed of light is accepted as constant for all reference frames and is symbolized by the constant “c”. However, according to **the reference frame of the object emitting the light**, the speed of the emitted light signal is often different from “c”. This is due to a phenomenon called the **Doppler Shift**, which changes the wavelength of the emitted light signal; the speed of the emitted signal is then determined by the **"Wave Speed"** equation.

WAVE SPEED EQUATION

Wave speed = Wavelength x Frequency of the wave

In this study, it has been set forth, based on the Wave Velocity and Doppler Shift equations, that the speed of light varies with respect to reference frames. This result has shown that, in the current Electromagnetic Theory, the approach I have called the **Alice Law** — based on the **(c+v) (c-v) mathematics** — should be taken as the foundation.

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II – INTRODUCTION

If the **Source Object** emitting the signal and the **Target Object** receiving it are **stationary** relative to each other, then according to the Source Object, the speed of the signal is constant, namely “**c**”.

$$c = \lambda \cdot f$$

If the Source Object and the Target Object are **stationary relative to each other**, then according to the reference frame of the Source Object, the speed of the emitted light signal is “**c**”.

However, if the Source Object and the Target Object are **moving relative to each other**, the emission frequency of the signal does not change, but the **wavelength of the signal changes**. In this case, since the wave speed will be determined according to the altered wavelength, the speed of the emitted signal will be different from the value “**c**”.

$$c' = \lambda' \cdot f$$

If the Source Object and the Target Object are **moving relative to each other**, then according to the reference frame of the Source Object, the speed of the emitted light signal is different from “**c**”.

For the **Target Object** receiving the signal, the situation is different. According to an object's own reference frame, **the speed of an incoming light signal is always constant and equal to “c”**. This is a result obtained through measurement, and in physics this is why the constant “**c**” exists.

$$c = \lambda \cdot f$$

If the Source Object and the Target Object are **stationary relative to each other**, then according to the Target Object's reference frame, the speed of the incoming light signal is equal to “**c**”. The wavelength and frequency of the incoming signal are the same as the wavelength and frequency values of the signal emitted by the Source Object.

However, if the Source Object and the Target Object are moving relative to each other, the speed of the light signal reaching the Target Object will still be “**c**”. However, due to the change in the wavelength of the emitted signal, for the Target Object, both the wavelength and the frequency of the incoming signal will be different.

$$c = \lambda' \cdot f'$$

If the Source Object and the Target Object are **moving relative to each other**, then according to the Target Object's reference frame, the speed of the incoming light signal is “**c**”, but the wavelength and frequency of the signal have changed.

In this study, it has been mathematically shown that light behaves as described here. As a result, in Electromagnetic Theory, it is necessary to switch to the mathematics shown here, called the (c+v) (c-v) mathematics.

III – METHOD AND FINDINGS

The Beginning of the Event, Figure 1:

As a starting point, I will describe an “Event” and then develop the topic.

As seen in the figure below, at position **A** there are three Target Objects (boxes) and at position **B** there are three Source Objects (lamps). The boxes are identical to each other. The lamps are identical to each other.

At the beginning of the event, the Target Objects and the Source Objects are **stationary** at their respective positions A and B.

The Event Starts, Figure 2:

All three lamps turn on at the same time, and simultaneously, Lamp 2 moves away from the boxes, while Lamp 3 moves towards the boxes. I denote the speed of the lamps as " v ". Both lamps move at the same speed but in opposite directions.

The Development of the Event, Figure 3

While the light emitted from the lamps travels toward their respective targets, Lamp 2 and Lamp 3 continue moving in their respective directions. I accept as a basic fact of physics that the speed of the light beams traveling toward the Target Objects is "c" relative to the targets. Since the lamps are located at position B and turn on at the same time, the distances between the boxes and the approaching light beams will always be equal.

End of the Event, Figure 4

Since the lights were turned on when the lamps were at position B, the lights reach their targets at position A at the same time and in a duration of "t" ($t = \frac{d_0}{c}$). For the moment when the lights arrive, I show on the figure the distances of the lamps from the boxes.

After expressing the dimensions mathematically, we can easily see that the statement that the speed of light is "c" in all reference frames is **not possible** and is fundamentally incorrect.

Here are the data we have obtained so far, presented in a table below.

VALUES TABLE

Light arrival time: $t = \frac{d_0}{c}$		
Distances between the Boxes and Lamps at the moment the lights reach the boxes:		
Box 1 - Lamp 1	$d_0 = c.t$	
Box 2 - Lamp 2	$d_2 = c.t + v.t = (c + v).t$	
Box 3 - Lamp 3	$d_1 = c.t - v.t = (c - v).t$	
Speeds of the light signals emitted by the lamps according to their own reference frames:		
Lamp 1	$c_0 = \frac{d_0}{t}$	$c_0 = c$
Lamp 2	$c_1 = (c + v) = \frac{d_2}{t}$	$c_1 > c$
Lamp 3	$c_2 = (c - v) = \frac{d_1}{t}$	$c_2 < c$
Speeds of the incoming light signals according to the boxes' own reference frames:		
Box 1	$c_0 = \frac{d_0}{t}$	$c_0 = c$
Box 2	$c_0 = \frac{d_0}{t}$	$c_0 = c$
Box 3	$c_0 = \frac{d_0}{t}$	$c_0 = c$

As seen in the “Values Table,” the **(c+v)** and **(c-v)** values refer, in meaning, to the **speeds** of the light signals emitted **according to the lamps' own reference frames**.

Because the speed of light varies according to reference frames, the speed of a light signal can only be accurately defined using the “**(c+v) (c-v) Mathematics**.” And the **Alice Law** is the Electromagnetic Theory that uses this mathematics. Therefore, when you state that you have adopted the “**Alice Law**,” you are in fact stating that you have adopted the **(c+v) (c-v) Mathematics**.

Universality of the Event, Figure 5

When describing the “Event,” I stated that in the initial state, the Lamps and Boxes were stationary. However, in the universe, no object is truly at rest. Even if the Lamps and Boxes are stationary relative to each other, this does not mean that they are not moving. Let us consider that the “Event” described here takes place within a higher-level frame of reference. This higher frame may be moving in any direction and at any speed. Nevertheless, the “Event” occurs exactly the same way, without any change. In physics, this is explained by the **Galilean Principle of Relativity**.

Galilean Principle of Relativity: *The fundamental laws of physics are the same in all reference frames moving at constant speed relative to one another.*

Therefore, in the “Event” described here, the values we calculated for distances and speeds are the correct ones to rely on. Since we have incorporated the Galilean Principle of Relativity into the logic of the “Event,” we can now formulate a consistent principle for the behavior of light as follows:

Universal Light Speed: *In empty space, light travels at the constant speed c , relative to the reference frame of its arrival target, regardless of the source emitting it.*

Event development and wavelengths, Figure 6

At this stage, by adding the wavelengths of the emitted light to the “Event” we are examining, we will reach important conclusions. Let us now express the distances d_0, d_1, d_2 in terms of wavelengths.

It was assumed that the lamps are identical to each other. Therefore, the frequencies of the light emitted from all three lamps are equal. Let us define this frequency value as f_0 . The frequency f_0 is a common value for all three lamps.

Let us assume that the photons forming the light from the lamps are emitted one by one and in succession by the lamps. We will number the photons according to their order of emission and, in addition, represent the wavelength of each photon as a complete sine wave. As shown in the figure below, photon number 1 is emitted, followed by photon number 2, and the emission of light continues in this manner. Let us assume that at the moment when the photons numbered 1 reach their targets, the emission of photons numbered “n” has been completed. Accordingly, at the moment of light arrival, the situation of the photons will be as shown in the figure below.

Let us pay attention here. Because the frequencies of the lamps are equal to each other, all three lamps have emitted “n” photons within the same time “t”. However, the wavelengths of the emitted light are not equal to each other. Since “Box 2 and Lamp 2” and “Box 3 and Lamp 3” are moving relative to each other, the wavelengths of the light signals emitted from Lamp 2 and Lamp 3 have changed.

If we take the wavelength of the light emitted from “Lamp 1” as a reference point;
 The wavelength of the light emitted from “Lamp 2” has **increased**.
 The wavelength of the light emitted from “Lamp 3” has **decreased**.

The change in wavelength caused by the relative motion between the Source Object and the Target Object is known in physics as the **Doppler Shift**, and the figure above illustrates the formation of the Doppler Shift. And again, note that when the lights (photons) are emitted, they are emitted with already **changed wavelengths**. In the Doppler Shift, the change in wavelength occurs in the Source Object and **during the emission of the light signal**.

The mathematical information given to us by the event

At this stage, we can use the data obtained from the figures to derive our mathematical results.

Light travel time:

$$t = \frac{d_0}{c}$$

Let the lamp's original wavelength be (λ_0) and its frequency (f_0). Let us accept these values as the lamp's manufacturing specifications. The product of these two values is equal to the constant “c.”

$$c = f_0 \cdot \lambda_0$$

Using the figure above, the wavelengths of the light can be calculated from the following equation:

$$\text{Wavelength} = \frac{\text{Distance}}{n}$$

Distance Table

Results obtained using speed values	Results obtained using wavelength values
$d_0 = c.t$	$d_0 = \lambda_0.n$
$d_1 = (c - v).t$	$d_1 = \lambda_1.n$
$d_2 = (c + v).t$	$d_2 = \lambda_2.n$

Deriving the Doppler Shift Equation:

Let us use the distance data we obtained to derive the Doppler Shift equation.

Deriving the Doppler Shift equation for the light from the Third Lamp:

(Source Object and Target Object are **approaching** each other)

$$d_0 = c.t = \lambda_0.n$$

$$d_1 = (c - v).t = \lambda_1.n$$

$$\frac{c.t}{(c - v).t} = \frac{\lambda_0.n}{\lambda_1.n} \implies \frac{c}{(c - v)} = \frac{\lambda_0}{\lambda_1} \implies$$

Doppler Shift 1

$\lambda_1 = \lambda_0 \cdot \frac{(c - v)}{c}$

Deriving the Doppler Shift equation for the light from the Second Lamp:
 (Source Object and Target Object are **moving away** from each other)

$$d_0 = c.t = \lambda_0.n$$

$$d_2 = (c + v).t = \lambda_2.n$$

$$\frac{c.t}{(c + v).t} = \frac{\lambda_0.n}{\lambda_2.n} \implies \frac{c}{(c + v)} = \frac{\lambda_0}{\lambda_2} \implies$$

Doppler Shift 2

$$\lambda_2 = \lambda_0 \cdot \frac{(c + v)}{c}$$

We can generalize the above Doppler Shift equations as follows. We have seen that the (c+v) and (c-v) values in the equations are the speeds of the signal sent according to the reference frame of the Source Object. Accordingly, we can write the General Doppler Shift equation as follows and in two forms. The equation on the left is still the Doppler Shift equation used in Classical Mechanics. The equation on the right is the new information introduced with the Alice Law.

General Doppler Shift Equations

$$\lambda' = \lambda \cdot \frac{(c \pm v)}{c}$$

$$\lambda' = \lambda \cdot \frac{c'}{c}$$

Symbol	Description
v :	c
c :	1 - Speed of light constant 2 - Speed of the signal reaching the Target Object according to the Target Object's reference frame. 3 - Speed of the signal sent by the Source Object to a stationary Target Object according to the Source Object's reference frame.
$c \pm v$:	Speed of the signal sent by the Source Object to a moving Target Object according to the Source Object's reference frame. $c \pm v$ Possible values of this expression: If the Source Object and the Target Object are moving away from each other: $c + v$ If the Source Object and the Target Object are approaching each other: $c - v$
c' :	Speed of the signal sent by the Source Object to a moving Target Object according to the Source Object's reference frame.
λ :	Original wavelength of the signal sent from the source to a stationary target.
λ' :	Altered wavelength of the signal sent from the source to a moving target.

Deriving Wave Speed Equations for Source and Target Objects:

First, let us rewrite here the general Doppler Shift equation we obtained above:

$$\lambda' = \lambda \cdot \frac{c'}{c}$$

1) According to the Source Object's own reference frame, write the speed of the light signal sent to a **stationary** Target Object:

$$c = \lambda \cdot f$$

2) Using the two equations above, according to the Source Object's own reference frame, write the speed of the light signal sent to a **moving** Target Object::

$$\lambda' = \lambda \cdot \frac{c'}{\lambda \cdot f} = \frac{c'}{f} \quad \Rightarrow \quad c' = \lambda' \cdot f$$

c' : According to the Source Object's own reference frame, the speed of the signal sent to the moving Target Object

λ' : The wavelength of the signal emitted from the Source Object that has undergone Doppler Shift

f : The emission frequency of the signal at the Source Object

3) According to the Target Object's reference frame, the wavelength of the signal coming from a **stationary** Source Object will not change. By measuring the wavelength of the incoming signal, we can find the signal's frequency. The frequency we obtain will be the same as the source's frequency. Then we can write the wave speed equation for the incoming signal:

$$f = \frac{c}{\lambda} \quad \Rightarrow \quad c = \lambda \cdot f$$

4) According to the Target Object's reference frame, if the signal it receives was emitted by a **moving** Source Object, the signal will still arrive with at speed “**c**”, but its wavelength will have changed due to the Doppler Shift. Let us define the changed wavelength as λ' . Then, by calculating the frequency, we can write the wave speed equation.

$$f' = \frac{c}{\lambda'} \quad \Rightarrow \quad \boxed{c = \lambda' \cdot f'}$$

c : According to the Target Object's own reference frame, the speed of the signal arriving from the moving Source Object

λ' : 1- The wavelength of the signal emitted by the Source Object. Due to the Doppler Shift, the wavelength has changed.
2- The wavelength of the signal arriving at the Target Object.

f' : For the Target Object, the frequency of the signal arriving at it.

SUMMARY TABLE

Wave Speed Equations for Electromagnetic Waves	
Wave speed equations for a signal emitted according to the Source Object's own reference frame:	
Source Object stationary	$c = \lambda \cdot f$
Target Object in motion	$c' = \lambda' \cdot f$
Wave speed equations for a signal received according to the Target Object's own reference frame:	
Source Object stationary	$c = \lambda \cdot f$
Source Object in motion	$c = \lambda' \cdot f'$

IV – RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

There is much that could be said here, but I will say only this:

Recognize the great mistake made in the past within the theory of physics and immediately turn to what is correct. The information provided in this publication falls within the scope of basic physics knowledge, and it is information that everyone engaged in the science of physics—whether amateur or professional, young or old, student or professor—must learn and understand. And of course, you will be responsible for this knowledge: personally, as an educator, and institutionally.

And I ask you earnestly, do not involve Albert Einstein in this matter. With both his truths and his errors, he expressed his own ideas. It is very clear from this publication that the Theory of Relativity is not a valid theory. What you need to do is to direct yourself toward what is correct.

V – REFERENCES

I found these publications about twenty-five years ago, when I first began working on the Alice Law. These publications are studies showing that things are not going well within the Theory of Relativity. Thanks to these works, I was able to find the strength to continue developing the Alice Law. I would like to thank the authors of these publications here.

The GPS and the Constant Velocity of Light

Paul Marmet, Professor, Physics, Laval University, Québec, Canada 1962-83, Senior Research Officer, National Research Council of Canada 1983-90

Successful GPS Operations Contradict the Two Principles of Special Relativity

and Imply a New Way for Inertial Navigation – Measuring Speed Directly

Ruyong Wang, St. Cloud State University, St. Cloud, Minnesota, United States

Clock Behavior and the Search for an Underlying Mechanism for Relativistic Phenomena

Ronald R. Hatch, NavCom Technology, Inc

Lunar Laser Ranging Test Of The Invariance Of C

Daniel Y. Gezari

NASA/Goddard Space Flight Center, Laboratory for ExoPlanets and Stellar Astrophysics,

One-Way Light Speed Determination Using the Range Measurement Equation of the GPS

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Resolving Spacecraft Earth-Flyby Anomalies with Measured Light Speed Anisotropy

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